

Review

Analysis and research on consumer purchasing behavior of electronic products in e-commerce platform

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Abstract: The rapid development of internet technology has led to significant changes in consumer behavior, particularly in the realm of electronic commerce (e-commerce). This study aims to understand the factors that influence consumer purchasing decisions for electronic products in the e-commerce environment. Utilizing a multiple linear regression model, the research analyzes a large dataset of consumer purchasing behavior to identify the key drivers of these decisions. The study focuses on variables such as user age, historical purchase frequency, page views, and average visit duration. These variables are analyzed to determine their impact on consumer purchasing intentions, which is quantified using actual purchase amounts or frequencies. The analysis reveals strong positive correlations between the target variable and user age, historical purchase frequency, and average visit duration, while the correlation with page views is weaker. Using SPSS25 software, the research conducts a stepwise multiple linear regression analysis, resulting in a model that includes average visit duration and historical purchase frequency as significant predictors. The final regression equation demonstrates that these two factors have a substantial impact on consumer purchasing behavior, with a high coefficient of determination (R^2) indicating a good fit of the model. The findings of this study provide valuable insights for e-commerce platforms looking to optimize their sales strategies and improve customer satisfaction. By understanding the key factors that drive consumer purchasing decisions, platforms can tailor their offerings, marketing strategies, and user experiences to better meet the needs and preferences of their customers.

Keywords: Electronic commerce; Purchasing decisions; Multiple linear regression

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I. Introduction

1.1 Research background and significance

With the rapid development of Internet technology, e-commerce has become an important part of the global economy, which has greatly changed people's shopping habits. In recent years, the explosive growth of e-commerce platforms has brought about an unprecedented competitive landscape, making understanding and predicting consumer purchasing behavior the key to gaining a competitive advantage. However, consumers' online purchase decision-making process is complex and changeable, and is influenced by many factors such as product features, price, promotions, user reviews,

and website design. Therefore, in-depth analysis of how these factors work together is crucial to optimize the product recommendation system, improve the user experience, and develop precision marketing strategies.

1.2 Research status

According to the literature reviewed in this paper, scholars have widely used statistics and machine learning methods to explore consumers' online shopping behaviors. For example, 1. Theoretical research on consumer behavior: Many scholars have explored the factors that affect consumers' purchasing behavior on e-commerce platforms from the perspectives of psychology^[1], economics^[2,3] and sociology^[4]. These factors include personal characteristics, social environment, product attributes, platform characteristics, etc. 2. Research on user experience of e-commerce platforms: Researchers pay attention to users' experience and perception on e-commerce platforms^[5], including influencing factors such as interface design, interaction design, information presentation and service quality^[6], as well as the influence of these factors on users' purchase intention and behavior. 3. Data analysis and model building: More and more studies have adopted data-driven methods to build purchase behavior prediction models or consumer portraits through big data analysis^[7], data mining^[8], machine learning^[9] and other technologies to reveal the rules and trends of consumer purchasing behaviors. 4. Research on mobile e-commerce: With the popularity of mobile Internet, mobile e-commerce has become one of the research hotspots^[10]. Scholars pay attention to the purchasing behavior characteristics of mobile users, the design optimization of mobile applications, and the security of mobile payments. 5. Cross-border e-commerce research: In recent years, the rapid rise of China's cross-border e-commerce market has attracted the attention of many researchers^[11,12]. The research content involves the user behavior characteristics of cross-border e-commerce platforms, the competition pattern of the international market, and the impact of the policy environment. 6. Research on social e-commerce: As an emerging model of e-commerce, social e-commerce has also attracted academic attention^[13,14]. The researchers explored the impact of social media on purchasing behavior, the business models of social e-commerce platforms, and the role of users' social networks. 7. Policy and regulatory studies: Some studies focus on the influence of government policies and regulations on e-commerce market and consumer purchasing behavior, as well as the regulatory role of policies on industry development and competition pattern^[15,16].

1.3 Research purpose and problem definition

The purpose of this study is to comprehensively analyze the key factors that affect the purchasing behavior of consumers on e-commerce platforms by establishing a multiple linear regression model, and to explore the interaction between them. Specific goals include: (1) Identifying the main factors that influence the purchase decision; (2) Quantify the impact of various factors on the purchasing behavior of different consumer groups; (3) Explore how to improve conversion rate and customer satisfaction by optimizing e-commerce platform strategies. The study will define consumer purchasing behavior, including not only the final purchase decision, but also the user's age, the number of historical purchases, the number of page views, and the average length of a user's visit.

1.4 Research methods and paper structure

This study adopts quantitative research method, mainly through the following steps:

Data collection: Obtain user behavior data, product information and transaction records from representative e-commerce platforms. Variable selection and data preprocessing: determine the influencing factors, carry out data cleaning, missing value processing and standardization.

Model construction and verification: Multiple linear regression model was applied to analyze the influence of various factors on consumers' purchasing decisions.

II. Overview of e-commerce platform

2.1 Development history and characteristics of e-commerce platform

The development of e-commerce platforms began in the early 1990s, with the commercialization of the Internet, the first batch of e-commerce platforms such as Alibaba began to emerge, mainly B2B (business-to-business) model. Subsequently, with the further maturity of e-commerce technology and the development of online payment systems, the B2C

(business-to-consumer) model gradually emerged, and platforms such as Amazon and Jingdong began to receive global attention. Entering the era of mobile Internet, e-commerce platform has ushered in new development opportunities, consumers can shop through mobile phones anytime and anywhere, and the user scale of the platform has further expanded. In recent years, O2O (online to offline) model has become a new trend in the development of e-commerce platforms, through the combination with offline physical stores, the platform can better meet the online and offline shopping needs of consumers.

The characteristics of e-commerce platform are mainly reflected in the following aspects:

1. Rich variety of goods: covering clothing, food, home, cosmetics, electrical appliances and other goods, consumers can easily search for the required goods.
2. Affordable price: Compared with traditional physical stores, e-commerce platforms are more competitive due to lower costs. At the same time, most platforms have also introduced membership systems, coupons and discount promotions, further reducing shopping costs.
3. Convenient operation: consumers can choose goods at home or anywhere else, pay online, inquire logistics information, etc., eliminating many tedious processes.
4. Safe and reliable: The e-commerce platform encrypts online payments to ensure payment security, and also provides after-sales service and dispute settlement mechanism to ensure consumers' shopping experience.

2.2 The role of e-commerce platforms in consumer shopping

E-commerce platforms play multiple roles in consumer shopping. First of all, the platform provides consumers with rich commodity information and convenient shopping channels, so that consumers can buy the goods they need anytime and anywhere. Second, the platform helps consumers make more informed shopping decisions through intelligent recommendations, user reviews and other functions. In addition, the e-commerce platform also provides consumers with perfect after-sales service and dispute settlement mechanism to ensure that the rights and interests of consumers are protected.

In the shopping process, e-commerce platforms build a bridge between consumers and sellers. Consumers can browse various products on the platform, compare prices and quality, and choose the most suitable products for them. At the same time, the platform also provides rich payment methods and logistics information inquiry functions, making the shopping process more convenient.

2.3 Challenges and opportunities facing e-commerce platforms

With the rapid development of e-commerce platform, it also faces many challenges. As market competition intensifies, e-commerce platforms need to constantly innovate and optimize to attract and retain consumers. At the same time, platforms also need to address issues such as data security and privacy protection to ensure that user information is not leaked or abused. In addition, the development of cross-border e-commerce has also brought new challenges and opportunities to e-commerce platforms.

However, challenges often come with opportunities. E-commerce platforms can accurately grasp consumer demand and market trends through big data analysis, artificial intelligence and other technical means, and provide more accurate marketing and promotion services for merchants. At the same time, with the popularity of mobile Internet and the development of Internet of Things technology, e-commerce platforms are expected to achieve a more intelligent and personalized shopping experience in the future.

In short, e-commerce platforms are playing an increasingly important role in consumer shopping, not only providing consumers with convenient shopping channels and rich commodity information, but also providing merchants with a broad market space and accurate marketing means. However, at the same time of rapid development, e-commerce platforms also need to constantly respond to challenges and seize opportunities to achieve sustainable development.

III. The theoretical framework of consumer purchasing behavior

3.1 Influencing factors of consumer purchasing behavior

Consumer purchasing behavior is affected by many factors, which can be roughly divided into two categories: internal factors and external factors.

Internal factors mainly include consumer characteristics, interests, purchasing preferences, needs, motivations, feelings, attitudes and learning. The characteristics of consumers refer to their age, gender, occupation, income and other basic conditions, which determine the basic needs and purchasing power of consumers. Interests and purchasing preferences reflect the consumer's preference for a certain type of goods or services. Consumers' needs generate purchasing motivation, and motivation is the direct driving force of consumers' purchasing behavior. Perception refers to a consumer's intuitive impression of a product or service, which influences their purchasing decision. Attitude is consumers' overall evaluation of goods or services, and a positive attitude often prompts consumers to make purchasing decisions. Learning is a process in which consumers accumulate experience and adjust their purchasing behavior in the process of buying and using goods.

The external factors mainly include enterprise marketing, related groups, social and cultural background and the characteristics of e-commerce platform. Corporate marketing influences consumers' purchasing decisions through advertising, promotion and other means. Relevant groups, such as family, friends, colleagues, etc., will also have an impact on consumers' purchasing behavior. Social and cultural background includes consumers' values, beliefs, customs, etc., which will affect consumers' purchasing preferences. The characteristics of e-commerce platforms, such as the reputation of the platform, the richness of goods, and the convenience of shopping, will also have an important impact on consumers' purchasing behavior.

3.2 Analysis of consumer purchasing decision-making process

The purchasing decision process of consumers is a complex and rational process, which usually includes the stages of problem identification, information collection, program evaluation, purchase decision and post-purchase behavior. In the problem identification phase, consumers define their needs and associate those needs with a specific product or service. Then, in the information gathering stage, consumers will obtain information about the product or service through various channels in order to better understand the market and the goods. In the program evaluation stage, consumers will evaluate the attributes, benefits and values of products or services according to the collected information, and form different purchase plans. Then, in the purchase decision stage, consumers will compare and choose between different purchase plans, and finally determine the purchase intention. Finally, in the post-purchase behavior stage, consumers will evaluate the purchased goods or services and form a feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction, which may affect their future purchase behavior.

3.3 Analysis of purchasing behavior of electronic products

In e-commerce, the analysis of consumers' purchasing behavior of electronic products can be started from the dimensions of user age, historical purchase number, page views (PV) and average visit time of users, which together reveal consumers' preferences, purchasing habits and online behavior patterns. The following is a framework for analyzing these dimensions:

1. User age

Consumer preferences: Consumers of different ages may have different preferences for electronic products. For example, younger users (e.g. 18-39 years old) may be more inclined to pursue trendy, high-performance electronics such as the latest smartphones, gaming devices, etc., while older users may be more focused on practicality and ease of use.

Purchasing power: In general, middle-aged users may have higher purchasing power and greater demand for high-end electronic products.

Embrace new technology: Younger people are more willing to try new technologies and products, while older users may be more conservative and prefer familiar brands and products.

2. Historical purchase times

Repeat purchase rate: Users who purchase electronics frequently may have high loyalty to the brand or a continuous need for electronics upgrades, which helps to identify potential high-value customers.

Purchase cycle: Analysis of user history purchase intervals can help predict the next purchase time and provide a basis for precision marketing.

Purchase preference: Users who have purchased specific types of electronic products several times may have special interests or needs for related products, and can push relevant product information.

3. Page Views (PV)

Degree of interest: A product page with a high number of page views indicates that users have a high interest in this type of product, which can be used as an indicator of product popularity and market demand.

Decision process: Users may repeatedly browse multiple product pages for comparison before purchasing, and the number of page views combined with residence time can infer the user's decision stage and hesitation point.

Content appeal: The content of a highly viewed page may be more in line with user preferences or more effectively convey product information, which can be a guide for optimizing product presentation and marketing strategies.

4. Average access duration of users

Engagement: Users who visit for a long time are likely to be more engaged with the platform or product and are potential buyers.

Information gathering: Long access times can also mean that users are scrutinizing product information and are at a critical stage in the decision making process.

Experience evaluation: Visit duration is closely related to the user experience of the website or APP, and a long time may reflect a friendly interface, clear navigation, or rich content.

3.4 New characteristics of consumer purchasing behavior under e-commerce platform

Under the e-commerce platform, consumer purchasing behavior presents some new characteristics. First, consumers are faced with more choices. E-commerce platforms provide a wealth of commodity information and services, consumers can easily compare the price of different platforms, brand reputation and commodity quality and other factors to choose the most suitable for their own goods. Secondly, the shopping environment is more convenient. Consumers can browse products and place orders anytime and anywhere through computers or mobile phones, regardless of time and space restrictions. In addition, e-commerce platforms usually provide shopping cart functions, consumers can put interested goods in the shopping cart, and then decide whether to buy, enhancing the flexibility of shopping.

At the same time, the consumer purchasing behavior under the e-commerce platform also pays more attention to individualization and customization. Consumers can search and screen products on the platform according to their needs and preferences to find the products that best meet their needs. In addition, some e-commerce platforms also provide personalized recommendation services to recommend products that may be of interest to consumers based on their purchase history and browsing behavior.

IV. Construction of multiple linear regression model

4.1 Theoretical basis of multiple linear regression model

A multiple linear regression model is a statistical analysis method used in statistics to study the linear relationship between a dependent variable (usually a continuous variable) and one or more independent variables (which can be continuous or categorical variables). Its theoretical basis involves the following core concepts:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_p X_p + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Y is the dependent variable (response variable); $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p$ are independent variables (explanatory variables); β_0 is the intercept term; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p$ is the coefficient corresponding to the independent variable; ε is the difference that represents the random variation that the model fails to account for, usually assumed to be an independent, equally distributed random variable with an expected value of 0 and a constant variance.

4.2 Variable selection and data collection

The data comes from user behavior records, browsing data on product detail pages, historical transaction records, and user survey questionnaires on e-commerce platforms, including but not limited to the following variables:

- (1) User Age (Continuously Variable, X1): The age of the user.
- (2) Continuous Variable, X2): The total number of historical purchases made by the user on the platform.
- (3) Page views (Continuously Variable, X3): The total number of page views by the user within a certain period.
- (4) Continuous Variable, Average User Access Time, X4): The average duration of user stay per visit to the platform.
- (5) Target variable: User purchase intention score (Continuous Variable), Y) , It can be quantified by the actual purchase amount or purchase frequency of the user over a period of time.

4.3 Final model establishment

Based on the actual situation, in the analysis of practical problems, there may be multiple sets of data, and formula (1) will be evolved into:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{n1} + \beta_2 X_{n2} + \dots + \beta_p X_{np} + \varepsilon_n \tag{2}$$

For more accuracy of the data, logarithm of the variable is taken, and the expression is as follows:

$$\ln y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln x_1 + \beta_2 \ln x_2 + \beta_3 \ln x_3 + \beta_4 \ln x_4 + \varepsilon \tag{3}$$

V. Analysis of consumer purchasing behavior

5.1 Correlation analysis

As shown in Table 1, the Person correlation coefficients of the four explanatory variables of user purchase intention $\ln y$ and user average visit duration $\ln x_1$, page views $\ln x_2$, historical purchase times $\ln x_3$ and user age $\ln x_4$ correspond to 0.933, 0.261, 0.967 and 0.987 successively, and their coefficients are all positive (positive correlation).

Table 1 Correlation analysis

Observed value	Pearson correlation	$\ln y$	$\ln x_1$	$\ln x_2$	$\ln x_3$	$\ln x_4$
$\ln y$	Significance (bilateral)	1	0.953**	0.271	0.947**	0.977**
			0.000	0.468	0.000	0.000
$\ln x_1$	Significance (bilateral)	0.933**	1	0.443	0.914**	0.935**
		0.000		0.200	0.000	0.000
$\ln x_2$	Significance (bilateral)	0.261	0.443	1	0.319	0.321
		0.448	0.200		0.370	0.356
$\ln x_3$	Significance (bilateral)	0.967**	0.914**	0.339	1	0.962**
		0.000	0.000	0.370		0.000
$\ln x_4$	Significance (bilateral)	0.987**	0.935**	0.321	0.962**	1
		0.000	0.000	0.366	0.000	

5.2 Empirical analysis of data

In order to find out the promoting factors of users' purchase intention, this paper uses SPSS25 software to conduct multiple linear regression analysis. The analysis results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 shows an overview of the effects of each predictor on the target variable. For example, a predictor (whose p-value is 0.985) has a negligible effect on the target variable, so it can be considered to exclude the variable from the model in subsequent model optimization.

When performing the "linear regression" function with SPSS software, a "step by step" approach was adopted, which initially included the predictor variables most closely associated with the target variables, and then identified and removed the predictor variables with the weakest influence in the current model. This process eventually resulted in ln_{x3} and ln_{x4} being included in the regression analysis, while ln_{x1} and ln_{x2} were not retained. For details, see Table 3.

It can be seen from Table 3 that the two groups of regression models are formed based on the sequential addition of ln_{x3} and ln_{x4}. Given that the determination coefficient R (0.996) of the second model is higher than that of the first model (0.948), the second model shows better adaptive performance.

As for Table 4, the significance level of model 2 is below the 0.05 threshold, confirming the overall validity of the regression equation and indicating that there is a significant correlation between the third and fourth predictor variables in the model and the target variables. In addition, the adjusted regression coefficient shows that the P-values of these two predictors are also below 0.05, which strongly proves that they have a significant impact on users' purchase inclination.

Table 2 Model summary

model	Non-standard coefficient B	Standard error	Standardization co-efficient Bate	co-T	P
(constant)	- 6.610	2.231		2.751	0.061
1 ln _{x1}	0.010	0.150	0.010	0.077	0.985
ln _{x2}	0.071	0.073	0.051	0.974	0.430
ln _{x3}	0.061	0.141	0.069	0.382	0.697
ln _{x4}	0.189	0.082	0.352	2.337	0.123

Table 3 Summary of the entry method model

model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Error in standard estimates
1	0.979	0.948	0.954	0.07394
2	0.998	0.996	0.995	0.02433

Table 4 Revised regression coefficients

model		Nonnormalized coefficient B	Standard error	Standardization co-efficient Bate	T	P
1	(constant)	- 15.065	1.812		- 8.316	0.000
	ln _{x4}	1.950	0.143	0.979	13.644	0.000
2	(constant)	- 4.869	1.346		- 3.862	0.006
	ln _{x3}	1.029	0.121	0.521	8.566	0.000
	ln _{x4}	0.251	0.030	0.497	8.180	0.000

The final regression equation is as follows:

$$\ln y = -4.869 + 1.029 \ln x_3 + 0.251 \ln x_4 \tag{4}$$

VI. Conclusions and Suggestions

6.1 Conclusion

According to the final equation (4), under the condition that the average user visit time, historical purchase times and user age remain unchanged, the purchase intention of users will increase by 1.029 percentage points for every 1 percentage point increase in page views. Therefore, gradually improve the number of page views, and actively optimize the attractiveness of e-commerce platforms, so as to promote the development of e-commerce and further contribute to social and economic growth.

From the final equation (4), if the number of page views, the number of historical purchases, and the age of the user are unchanged, every 1 percentage point increase in the average visit time of the user can increase by 0.251 percentage points. Therefore, it is necessary to continuously improve the turnover capacity of goods and better serve the development of e-commerce, thus promoting sustainable economic development.

6.2 E-commerce platform optimization direction for consumer purchase behavior

Based on the above analysis, e-commerce platforms can adopt the following strategies:

- (1) Optimize user experience and extend user access time.
- (2) Launch more customized promotions for active buyers.
- (3) Continuously improve user satisfaction to enhance purchase intention.
- (4) Customize product push according to user age to enhance purchase intention.

This example shows how multiple linear regression models can be used to analyze user behavior data on e-commerce platforms to predict and understand user purchase intentions, providing data support for more effective marketing and user retention strategies.

6.3 E-commerce platform marketing strategy innovation

With the intensification of market competition and changes in consumer demand, e-commerce platforms need to constantly innovate marketing strategies to attract and retain users. Here are some innovative marketing strategies:

First, we focus on the application of content marketing. By writing high-quality shopping guides, product reviews, industry trend analysis and other content, guide users to understand and pay attention to the products and services on the platform. At the same time, we also work with well-known bloggers, influencers and others to leverage their influence to expand brand exposure and user engagement.

Second, we launched customized marketing campaigns. According to the characteristics and needs of different user groups, develop personalized promotion programs, such as limited time discounts, full reduction offers, members enjoy. These activities can stimulate users' desire to buy and increase the conversion rate of purchases.

In addition, we are actively exploring cross-border cooperation and integrated marketing. Cooperate with other industries or brands to jointly launch joint products, cross-border activities, etc., and expand market share and brand influence through resource integration and complementary advantages.

Finally, we value data-driven marketing strategies. Through the analysis and mining of user behavior data and purchase data, we can deeply understand user needs and purchasing habits, and provide strong support for the formulation of marketing strategies. At the same time, we also use big data technology to accurately position users to achieve personalized marketing and precise push.

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